

GL MICAVE

D8.3. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

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Executive summary

The GLOMICAVE project creates a cloud-based platform that utilizes Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence to explore the relationship between genotypes and phenotypes using extensive omics datasets. The project has been committed to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, ensuring its developments are user-friendly, ethically sound, and socially responsible. Key features include stakeholder engagement and strong governance, ensuring alignment with ethical standards and societal expectations. GLOMICAVE represents an integrative approach to biotechnological innovation, promoting accessibility, scientific advancement, and societal benefit.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>BDA</i>	<i>Big Data Analytics</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>GDPR</i>	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
<i>ELSI</i>	<i>Ethical, legal and social implications</i>
<i>FAIR</i>	<i>findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability</i>
<i>EEA</i>	<i>European Economic Area</i>
<i>ML</i>	<i>Machine Learning</i>
<i>IPR</i>	<i>Intellectual Property Rights</i>

1. The GLOMICAVE project

The GLOMICAVE project addresses the need for building systems that allow scaling analytical processes of primary data and supporting downstream large-scale omics experiments, by maximizing the utility of pre-existing massive omics datasets to increase the understanding of biological systems as a whole, going beyond current existing data-driven tools in the biomedical sector.

The main objective of GLOMICAVE is to develop a cloud-based genotype-to-phenotype platform – relying on Big Data Analytics (BDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques – and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omics datasets, enhanced with automatic processing of scientific literature.

The main outcome will be a multi-omics data analysis platform consisting of multiple tools to assist experts and non-experts in identifying and understanding new links between genotype and phenotype, which apply to different domains. The platform will tackle data integration, analysis, and exploitation, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring.

GLOMICAVE’s integrative approach is validated in 3 different industrial sectors (livestock, agrobiotechnology and environment) addressing specific challenges in 6 business cases (animal reproductive technology, meat quality, fruit growth and quality (including tree viral infection status), plant growth, phosphorus removal/recovery and bioenergy production in the urban water cycle, which will pave the way for further uptake in other business areas.

2. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

The EU Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) plan is a framework that aims to ensure research and innovation activities are socially responsible, inclusive, and sustainable. The plan is based on the idea that research and innovation should be conducted in a way that considers the needs and values of society, and it should be done in a way that is transparent, open, and accessible to all.

The RRI plan is part of the Europe 2020 strategy which aims to create a smarter, greener economy where prosperity comes from research and innovation.¹ The plan is designed to help researchers and innovators to work together with stakeholders such as citizens, civil society organizations, and policymakers to identify the needs of society and to develop solutions that are socially responsible.²

Figure 1: Responsible Research and Innovation (Source: GREAT Project (<https://www.great-project.eu/>))

¹Responsible research and innovation, Europe's ability to respond to societal challenges <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2be36f74-b490-409e-bb60-12fd438100fe>

² European Commission, Research and innovation strategy 2020-2024 (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024_en)

The EU's RRI plan is built upon a set of principles that guide research and innovation activities. By adhering to these principles, the EU aims to ensure that research and innovation outcomes are aligned with societal values and contribute to sustainable development. These principles are the following:³

a) **Governance:** Effective governance in RRI involves implementing mechanisms that ensure that research and innovation processes are reflective of, and responsive to, societal needs and values. This includes creating frameworks for accountability, adaptability, and responsive public policy that guides science and technology in a direction beneficial to society as a whole.

b) **Public Engagement:** RRI insists on active and inclusive engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders, including the public, during research and innovation processes. Public engagement facilitates a mutual learning process between researchers and societal groups, ensuring that different perspectives are considered in shaping research agendas and outcomes.

c) **Gender Equality:** Gender equality is a fundamental principle in RRI, addressing the need for balanced gender representation in research activities and considering gender dimensions within research content. This principle ensures that research and its subsequent benefits address the needs and abilities of all genders.

d) **Science Education:** Promoting science education is essential in RRI to enhance public understanding and inclusion in science. This involves developing educational programs and materials that are accessible and relevant to diverse societal groups, thereby fostering a well-informed public that can actively participate in scientific and technological discourse.

e) **Open Access:** Open access to research results is a critical component of RRI, promoting transparency and accessibility of scientific information. This principle supports the dissemination of knowledge freely to all layers of society, facilitating broader societal participation in science and innovation processes.

f) **Ethics:** Ethics in RRI goes beyond compliance with legal standards, involving a proactive commitment to respecting fundamental rights and values throughout the research process. Ethical research considers issues like privacy, environmental impact, and social implications, ensuring that research practices and outcomes are morally sound.

3. Governance

Governance within the GLOMICAVE project is a cornerstone of its success, ensuring that the project not only advances scientifically but also adheres to high ethical and operational standards.

Principles of Governance in GLOMICAVE:

a) **Adherence to Regulatory Standards:** GLOMICAVE operates under strict compliance with EU regulations, such as GDPR and the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. This compliance ensures that all research activities and technological developments respect privacy, ethical standards, and legal requirements.

b) **Transparent and Inclusive Decision-Making:** The governance model of GLOMICAVE promotes transparency and inclusiveness, allowing for diverse perspectives in decision-making processes. This approach is instrumental in fostering an environment where all

³ Mazzonetto, M. and Simone, A. (2018). Introduction to "Science, society and citizens: suggestions (and hopes) on how to foster RRI in Horizon Europe" JCOM 17(03), C01. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.17030301>

contributions are valued, and collaborative solutions are developed, enhancing the project's impact and acceptability.

c) **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regular monitoring and evaluation are integral to the governance of GLOMICAVE. These processes ensure that the project meets its objectives efficiently and adapts to new challenges and insights. The feedback mechanisms in place allow for continual refinement of strategies and methodologies, crucial for maintaining relevance and efficacy in rapidly evolving research areas.

4. Public Engagement and Open Science

The EU recognizes the importance of engaging the public in research and innovation to ensure transparency, legitimacy, and social acceptance. The RRI plan encourages researchers and innovators to involve citizens in decision-making processes, enabling them to contribute their perspectives, values, and concerns. Through dialogue and participatory approaches, the EU aims to bridge the gap between science and society, fostering mutual understanding and trust. A key aspect of governance in GLOMICAVE involves continuous stakeholder engagement, which is critical to the project's iterative development process. By involving scientists, industry experts, and end-users through participatory methodologies, the project ensures that the tools and findings are not only scientifically robust but also aligned with user needs and societal values.

Public Engagement in GLOMICAVE

End-users and target beneficiaries (e.g. scientists and industry as main potential users) have been contributing to the development of the platform through the implementation of iterative and inclusive participatory multi-actor participatory methodologies as part of WP9 (Task 9.3 – Innovation management) as well as through demonstration training workshops in order to align GLOMICAVE platform development to meet end users' needs.

Open science in GLOMICAVE

Open access to research outputs, such as publications, data, and software, is a fundamental aspect of the EU's RRI plan. The EU encourages researchers and innovators to make their findings and data publicly available, promoting transparency and enabling wider access to knowledge. Open access facilitates collaboration, innovation, and the reproducibility of research, ultimately accelerating scientific progress.

Below, we just highlight some of the most important scientific and communication activities. The detailed description of them can be found in the WP7 deliverables, especially in D7.8.

Table 1 Publications in GLOMICAVE

TYPE	TITLE	PARTNERS INVOLVED	JOURNAL or CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS	DOI	STATUS
Article in Journal	The recipient metabolome explains the asymmetric ovarian impact on fetal sex development after embryo transfer in cattle	SERIDA, ELIANCE	Journal of Animal Science, 102 (2024)	https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skae081	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Computational Expansion of High-Resolution-MSn Spectral Libraries	EUT	Analytical Chemistry, 0 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.3c03343	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Enzyme-based kinetic modelling of ASC–GSH cycle during tomato fruit development reveals the importance of reducing power and ROS availability	INRAE	New Phytologist, Volume 240, Issue 1 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.19160	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Comparative constraint-based modelling of fruit development across species highlights nitrogen metabolism in the growth-defence trade-off	INRAE	The Plant Journal (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16409	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Biomarker metabolite mating of viable frozen-thawed IVP bovine embryos with pregnancy-competent recipients leads to improved birth rates	SERIDA, ELIANCE	Journal of Dairy Science (May 2023)	https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-23082	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Fitness of calves born from in vitro-produced fresh and cryopreserved embryos	SERIDA	Frontiers in Veterinary Science (November 2022)	https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.1006995	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	UPIMAP1, reCOGnizer and KEGGCharter: Bioinformatics tools for functional annotation and visualization of (meta)-omics datasets	UMINHO	Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal (April 2022)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2022.03.042	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Machine Learning-Based Retention Time Prediction of Trimethylsilyl Derivatives of Metabolites	EUT	Biomedicines Journal (MDPI), Special Issue: Omics Data Analysis and Integration in Complex Diseases (April 2022)	https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines10040879	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Predictive metabolomics of multiple Atacama plant species unveils a core set of generic metabolites for extreme climate resilience	INRAE	New Phytologist Journal (March 2022)	https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18095	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	The metabolic signature of in vitro produced bovine embryos helps predict pregnancy and birth after embryo transfer	SERIDA	Metabolites Journal (MDPI), Section “Endocrinology and Clinical Metabolic Research” (July 2021)	https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo11080484	PUBLISHED

Workshop on the methodology for the construction of omics-related graphs from animal, vegetal and environmental omic data: The objective of this Workshop was the development of one CEN Workshop Agreement on the methodology to follow for the construction of graphs on topics related to non-human omics data, specifically in the domain of semantics for animals, plant, and environment. This methodology provides guidance for the representation and analysis of omics data in these domains, to facilitate understanding and discovery of relevant relationships and patterns.⁴

5. Gender Equality

The EU is committed to promoting gender equality in research and innovation. The RRI plan emphasizes the importance of equal opportunities and representation for women and men in all stages of the research and innovation process. The EU actively works to address gender imbalances, biases, and stereotypes, fostering an inclusive research and innovation ecosystem that harnesses diverse talent and perspectives.

The GLOMICAVE project is gender neutral regarding the topic of research as it is not focused on humans and its outcome does not have an indirect gender-specific implication in humans. For the livestock casework, the livestock gender is defined as females (for the animal reproductive case) and males (for meat quality). With respect to operational practises within the project, all project partners have (or will deploy) measures for (i) ensuring equal opportunities in relation to human resources processes (e.g. recruitment, training, promotion, work-life balance, etc.), (ii) addressing gender-related biases and under-representation; and, (iii) carrying out gender-sensitive research and innovation by promoting a balanced gender composition of the staff working in projects. GLOMICAVE counts with a gender-balanced research staff and decision-making structure: it is led by females as project coordinator and project supervisor, from EURECAT, with a consortium where 49% are women, 26 out of 53.

6. Ethics

Ethics is a core principle of the EU's RRI plan, ensuring that research and innovation activities are conducted in line with ethical standards and respect for human rights. The EU expects researchers and innovators to adhere to ethical guidelines and frameworks, particularly when working with sensitive data, human subjects, or emerging technologies. The RRI plan promotes responsible practices that prioritize the well-being and rights of individuals and communities.

6.1 Ethics related to animals

The Directive 2010/63/EU⁵ is an EU legislation that sets out the rules for the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. It is one of the most stringent animal welfare laws in the world and has been praised by animal welfare groups for its commitment to reducing the use of animals in research.

The Directive is based on three key principles:

a) **Replacement:** This principle states that animals should not be used in scientific procedures if alternative methods are available. This could include computer models, cell cultures, or other non-animal methods.

⁴ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2023/workshop/2023-10-11-omics/>

⁵ Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes Text with EEA relevance

b) **Reduction:** This principle states that the number of animals used in scientific procedures should be minimized. This could be achieved by using techniques that require fewer animals, such as microdosing or in vitro models.

c) **Refinement:** This principle states that the welfare of animals used in scientific procedures should be maximized. This could be achieved by providing animals with appropriate housing, nutrition, and care, and by minimizing pain and distress.

Scope of the Directive

The Directive **applies to all animals used in scientific procedures**, including rodents, birds, fish, and mammals. It also applies to animals bred specifically so that their organs or tissues may be used for scientific purposes.

Procedures covered by the Directive

The Directive covers a wide range of scientific procedures, including:

Experimentation: This includes procedures that are carried out to obtain new knowledge or to test the safety or efficacy of products or procedures.

Training and teaching: This includes procedures that are carried out to train or teach students or researchers.

Diagnostic or therapeutic procedures: This includes procedures that are carried out to diagnose or treat diseases or conditions in animals.

Authorisation of procedures

Before any animal can be used in a scientific procedure, the **procedure must be authorized by an ethical review committee**. The ethical review committee will assess the scientific justification for the procedure, the potential benefits to humans or animals, and the potential harm to the animals.

Enforcement of the Directive

Member States are responsible for enforcing the Directive in their own countries. This includes monitoring the use of animals in scientific procedures, investigating complaints, and acting against those who breach the law.

All The partners in have acquired approval from Ethical Review Boards for their research.

6.2 Ethics related to plants

While ethical guidelines apply to the domain of plant research, concerns about informed consent, privacy, and harm to research subjects are generally less complex than for example human research. Ethics in plant research involves considerations of the social, moral, and environmental implications of studying and manipulating plants.

Plant research often intersects with environmental concerns particularly in terms of the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs). Considerations should include assessing the potential ecological impact of GMOs while adhering to local policies. In addition, invasive species, and habitat destruction resulting from agricultural practices are other important topics which fall under 'environmental concerns'.

Researchers should also promote sustainable agricultural practices that ensure food security while minimising environmental degradation, resource depletion, and harm to ecosystems. This includes promoting biodiversity, soil health, and water conservation. Researchers should strive

for equitable distribution of benefits and address issues of food insecurity and agricultural inequities. From the perspective of data generated from research; this should follow the FAIR (accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) principle whereby the greater research community can benefit. Ethical plant research should additionally promote public engagement and education on the importance of plant biodiversity, conservation, and sustainable agriculture. Researchers should engage with diverse stakeholders, foster dialogue, and address public concerns about emerging technologies and ethical dilemmas in plant research.

6.3 AI

The European Commission appointed a group of experts to provide advice on its AI strategy, Forming the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG)⁶, members include representatives from academia, civil society and industry.

Trustworthy AI has three components, which should be met throughout the system's entire life cycle:

- (i) it should be **lawful**, complying with all applicable laws and regulations;
- (ii) it should be ethical, ensuring adherence to **ethical** principles and values and
- (iii) it should be **robust**, both from a technical and social perspective since, even with good intentions, AI systems can cause unintentional harm. Each component in itself is necessary but not sufficient for the achievement of Trustworthy AI.

Ideally, all three components work in harmony and overlap in their operation. If, in practice, tensions arise between these components, society should endeavour to align them.⁷

The AI HLEG provided the following guidance on how trustworthy AI can be realised, by listing seven requirements that AI systems should meet. Both technical and non-technical methods can be used for their implementation.⁸

- i) Ensure that the development, deployment and use of **AI systems meets the seven key requirements for Trustworthy AI**: (1) human agency and oversight, (2) technical robustness and safety, (3) privacy and data governance, (4) transparency, (5) diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, (6) environmental and societal well-being and (7) accountability.
- ii) Consider **technical and non-technical methods** to ensure the implementation of those requirements.
- iii) Foster **research and innovation** to help assess AI systems and to further the achievement of the requirements; disseminate results and open questions to the wider public, and systematically train a new generation of experts in AI ethics.
- iv) **Communicate**, in a clear and proactive manner, information to stakeholders **about the AI system's capabilities and limitations**, enabling realistic expectation setting, and about the manner in which the requirements are implemented. Be transparent about the fact that they are dealing with an AI system.
- v) Facilitate the **traceability and auditability** of AI systems, particularly in critical contexts or situations.
- vi) **Involve stakeholders** throughout the AI systems life cycle. Foster training and education so that all stakeholders are aware of and trained in Trustworthy AI.
- vii) Be mindful that there **might be fundamental tensions between different principles** and requirements. Continuously identify, evaluate, document and communicate these trade-offs and their solutions.

The proposed AI Act

The EU Artificial Intelligence Act: Overview and Implications for Research and Development

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/expert-group-ai>

⁷ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI, 2019

⁸ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, 2018, p. 6.

As the digital landscape evolves, the EU has recognized the need for comprehensive regulations to address the growing influence and risks associated with AI. The proposed EU AI Act, first introduced in April 2021, is set to create one of the world's first sets of legal standards governing the development and deployment of AI technologies.

The proposed AI Act categorizes AI systems according to the risk they pose to safety and fundamental rights, ranging from minimal risk to unacceptable risk. This risk-based approach dictates the regulatory requirements for each category:

- **Unacceptable Risk:** AI applications that manipulate human behavior to circumvent users' free will are banned.
- **High-Risk:** AI systems in critical sectors such as healthcare, policing, and transport must undergo strict compliance checks before deployment. This includes ensuring data governance, transparency, and providing detailed documentation to trace the AI's decision-making process.
- **Limited Risk:** AI applications like chatbots must be transparent; users should be informed that they are interacting with a machine.
- **Minimal Risk:** For AI applications deemed to pose minimal risk, such as spam filters, the regulation imposes no additional requirements beyond existing laws.

To align with the AI Act, research projects must develop strategies that include:

- **Risk Assessment:** Early and ongoing assessments to classify AI systems according to the defined risk levels.
- **Transparency Measures:** Development of mechanisms to explain AI decisions to end-users, particularly when using AI in sensitive areas.
- **Data Governance:** Implementation of strict data handling procedures to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of data used by AI systems.

Scientific Research Exemptions in the EU AI Act

The latest version of the proposed EU AI Act includes important provisions that specifically address the use of AI in scientific research. Recognizing the unique needs and benefits of AI applications in the research sector, the legislation aims to facilitate innovation while ensuring that such technologies are used responsibly and ethically within the scientific community. To support scientific advancement and innovation, the **Act provides exemptions for AI systems used exclusively for scientific research purposes**. These exemptions are designed to alleviate some of the regulatory burdens that might hinder the development and application of AI in research settings.

AI systems developed and deployed for the purpose of scientific research may be exempt from some of the stringent compliance checks required for high-risk categories. This includes certain assessments of risk and bias that might be mandatory for commercial AI applications. By reducing these requirements, the Act facilitates a more agile research environment where scientists can experiment and innovate with fewer administrative hurdles.

While the Act provides exemptions, it also emphasizes the **need for ethical oversight** to ensure that research AI systems are developed and used in a manner that respects fundamental rights and safety standards. Institutions are encouraged to establish internal review boards or similar bodies to oversee AI research activities, mirroring the ethical oversight commonly associated with biomedical research.

For the GLOMICAVE project and similar research initiatives, these exemptions not only reduce regulatory burdens but also open new avenues for scientific exploration and progress. As the legislative process progresses and the Act nears implementation, staying informed and prepared to adapt to these regulations will be key to maximizing the benefits of AI in research. However, as the AI Act progresses through the EU legislative process, modifications are likely before its final adoption.

Figure 2: Framework for Trustworthy AI⁹

7. Science Education

The European Commission recognizes the importance of nurturing talent, improving skills, and fostering knowledge transfer to advance research, innovation, and societal development. In the context of a H2020 project, the Education Principle refers to the emphasis on promoting education, training, and capacity-building activities as an integral part of the project's objectives.

Science education also aims boosting the proficiency of individuals involved in research, enhancing their capabilities to produce valuable knowledge and achieve positive commercial results. It adds to the credibility of researchers and their affiliated organizations while also ensuring ongoing opportunities for knowledge building and skill development. Additionally, it has the potential to improve the effectiveness and suitability of innovation efforts.¹⁰

The dissemination and communication activities, detailed in WP7 deliverables, contributed to these efforts.

8. Summary

The EU's Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) plan provides a framework for integrating ethical considerations, societal needs, and stakeholder engagement into research and innovation activities. Throughout its execution, GLOMICAIVE makes significant efforts to adhere to the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), ensuring that activities have been conducted with ethical integrity, transparency, and public engagement. The project is fostering inclusive stakeholder participation, which has been instrumental in aligning the platform's development with real-world needs and societal values.

⁹ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, 2018, p. 10.

¹⁰ GREAT PROJECT